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Unraveling Nanoarchitectonics-Driven Metal–Support Interactions and Size Effects Governing CO Oxidation Activity of Size-Selected Pt Clusters on TiO₂ and SnO₂ Supports

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ABSTRACT

Supported size-selected clusters represent a unique class of materials offering high tunability of the chemical properties with high efficiency of material utilization. Herein, Pt_{*n*} (*n* = 13, 40) clusters supported on two technologically relevant supports, TiO₂ and SnO₂, were studied for CO oxidation under atmospheric pressure conditions. The catalytic activity was found to be directly influenced by both cluster size and support material, with Pt₄₀/TiO₂ showing the highest activity. In situ near-ambient-pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) revealed that, in general, a higher metallicity of the clusters promotes catalytic activity. However, the final oxidation state of Pt does not solely determine the activity, which rather evolves from a combination of factors, including strong metal–support interactions (SMSI) and size-dependent effects. Ex situ XPS and ion scattering spectroscopy (ISS) measurements on used catalysts highlighted the role of SMSI, particularly in the case of SnO₂, where SnO₂ overgrowth was suggested to enhance chemical stability and sintering resistance, as witnessed by stability tests conducted using NAP-XPS. However, this overgrowth also limited access to active Pt sites, reducing CO adsorption and O₂ activation, ultimately leading to lower catalytic activity of Pt_{*n*}/SnO₂ compared to TiO₂-supported catalysts.

1 | Introduction

Noble metal nanoparticles stabilized on oxide supports represent an important class of catalysts due to their high activity in a variety of catalytic reactions. Among these, CO oxidation is a widely studied model reaction, serving as a benchmark for understanding catalytic reactivity. In general, the reactivity of d-metals in CO oxidation is well understood and proceeds through the

Langmuir–Hinshelwood mechanism [1, 2]. In this context, Pt is one of the most studied and widely employed catalysts [3], but its prohibitive cost and low abundance drastically limit its future technological applications. Therefore, there is a constant need to enhance precious metal utilization efficiency, for example, by reducing the particle size and/or implementing nanoarchitectonics approaches [4–7]. However, despite significant advancements, the behavior of small particles measuring just

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a few nanometers or less under realistic reaction conditions remains a largely unexplored area of research.

For this reason, the application and study of size-selected clusters in the sub- and low-nanometer scale is of considerable interest in the field of catalysis. These small clusters offer numerous advantages providing a wide range of tunability of the catalytic properties with cluster size [8], where quantum effects play a substantial role in determining catalytic activity [9], even when changing the cluster size by only one atom [10]. For instance, the electronic structure of these particles is discrete rather than continuous, influencing how they interact with support materials and their ability to adsorb and dissociate reactant molecules such as CO and O₂ with respect to their bulk and crystalline counterparts [11–13]. This can result in increased reactivity and selectivity, allowing for more efficient chemical transformations [14, 15]. In addition, clusters are rich in undercoordinated atoms and their surface-to-bulk ratio approaches infinity, with the majority of the atoms being exposed to the reactants [16, 17]. This allows to drastically increase the material efficiency and reduces the amount of precious metals required, therefore minimizing the environmental and economic impact in the field of catalysis [18].

In this study, we choose two different cluster sizes, Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀. First, Pt₁₃ clusters possess electronic and geometric shell closures, contributing to their overall stability, and a unique bonding nature [19], whereas Pt₄₀ are in a low-nanometer scale, thus bridging the gap between the subnanometer (<1 nm in diameter) and nanometer (>1 nm in diameter) size regime.

The atomic and electronic structure of Pt clusters were initially studied by DFT calculations in the gas phase [20–24], and more recently on various supports capable of stabilizing small clusters on their surface [25, 26] and to affect their performance through synergistic metal–support interactions [27]. For these needs, we choose TiO₂ and SnO₂ as two technologically relevant supports. The interaction between Pt clusters and these oxides is expected to play a crucial role in determining their catalytic activity. Specifically, TiO₂ can form oxygen vacancies up to Ti₂O₃ or TiO at mild reduction conditions, which can promote strong metal–support interaction (SMSI) and facilitate charge transfer to the supported metal particles [28, 29]. In contrast, SnO₂ possesses lower reducibility in comparison with TiO₂ which may result in stronger Pt binding, leading to more effective cluster stabilization and distinct alterations in the electronic properties of Pt [29–31]. These differences in electronic interactions are of great importance as they can influence the adsorption energy of CO and the activation of oxygen, which are critical steps in CO oxidation.

In this combined catalytic and spectroscopic study, we utilize a state-of-the-art setup for temperature programmed reaction (TPR) under realistic reaction conditions and in situ near-ambient-pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) to investigate size-selected Pt_{*n*} clusters (*n* = 13, 40) deposited on SnO₂ and TiO₂ ultra-thin films during CO oxidation. Finally, a selected spent catalyst (Pt₄₀/SnO₂) was characterized ex situ by XPS in combination with ion scattering spectroscopy (ISS) to elucidate the role of SMSI on its performance. The schematic outlook of the experiment is shown in Figure 1a–d. The effects of cluster size and the nature of support material on the resulting catalytic activity are discussed with a focus on the evolution of the chemical state of the catalysts and the related

electronic state effects, with the ultimate goal of disentangling the key factors that determine the performance of small size-selected clusters. A fundamental understanding of these processes is crucial for efficient precious metal utilization and achieving tunable reactivity through precise control over the local coordination environment of active sites.

2 | Results

Atomically precise size-selected Pt_{*n*} (*n* = 13, 40) clusters were synthesized in the gas phase utilizing a vacuum apparatus based on magnetron sputtering and size-selection by quadrupole mass analyzer (see schematic representation in Figure 1a and related mass spectra in Figure S1) [15]. Clusters were deposited in the soft-landing regime with a kinetic energy below 1 eV per atom to avoid cluster fragmentation upon impact (though support-driven structural relaxation is still expected). As shown in Figure 1a, four catalytic systems were prepared, with clusters deposited onto two different technologically relevant supports, TiO₂ and SnO₂ films (thickness of 1.5 nm) grown by atomic layer deposition (ALD) on silicon chips [14]. Both films revealed relatively smooth morphology with the mean roughness (*R_a*) of 0.1 and 0.2 nm for TiO₂ and SnO₂, respectively (see atomic force microscopy (AFM) images in Figure S2). *R_a* for blank silicon with native surface oxide was 0.1 nm. Low energy He⁺ scattering (ISS) discussed below showed negligible Si intensity, implying that the TiO₂ and SnO₂ films are continuous in accord with electrochemical data [32].

For catalytic tests and NAP-XPS measurements, the cluster coverage was kept at 10% of an atomic monolayer (ML) for Pt₁₃ and 20% ML for Pt₄₀, corresponding to 31 and 62 ng of catalyst, respectively, and to an estimated average cluster-to-cluster distance of 3.3 nm for Pt₁₃ and 4.1 nm for Pt₄₀ (assuming spherical clusters on the flat surface).

The size and distribution of Pt₄₀ clusters deposited on holey carbon (h.c.) coated copper grids were studied by high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and are presented in Figure 1e–g. For this need, we kept the coverage at 0.1% ML to avoid agglomeration on the carbon-based support. The HAADF STEM overview image in Figure 1e shows that the clusters are homogeneously distributed on the surface of the h.c. with a density of 200 clusters per ~0.1 μm² which corresponds to the number of clusters expected for the deposited coverage. The average size of the Pt₄₀ clusters estimated as equivalent to the diameter of the disk encircling the cluster was approximately 1.5 nm in diameter. As witnessed by STEM in Figure 1f, the long-time exposure to high fluxes of electrons with an energy of 200 keV leads to the cluster's disintegration on the carbon base support. This confirms the cluster size defined by quadrupole mass filtering, as the clusters disintegrate into exactly 40 atoms (see Figure 1f, cluster 3). To further study the effect of the support on cluster confinement on the surface, Pt₄₀ clusters were deposited on a 1.5 nm thick TiO₂ layer grown by ALD on an h.c. grid. As shown in Figure 1g, the cluster maintains a 3D-like structure consisting of a few layers of rather randomly distributed atoms, with the size of the clusters similar to the one measured on h.c. (approximately 1.5 nm in diameter). The layer of TiO₂ support remains amorphous with some locally distinguished crystalline structures.

FIGURE 1 | Top: Schematic outlook of the experiment. (a) Pt clusters synthesis process using molecular beam in the gas phase and corresponding representative mass spectrum; (b) catalytic testing using TPR; (c) NAP-XPS in situ characterization under equivalent conditions; and (d) ex situ XPS and ISS surface characterization of spent catalysts. Bottom images, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) images of Pt₄₀ clusters deposited on h.c. coated copper grids obtained using high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) technique, namely (e) overview image showing the distribution of the clusters with the coverage of 0.1% ML; (f) high resolution STEM image showing 3 clusters, acquired with a beam energy of 200 keV but using different electron doses (1-low, 2-moderate, and 3-high), where longer exposure to the beam leads to clusters disintegration; (g) Pt₄₀ clusters supported on a 1.5-nm layer of TiO₂ layer predeposited onto a h.c. copper grid for STEM imaging.

2.1 | Catalytic Tests

The catalytic activity of Pt_{*n*} (*n* = 13, 40) supported on TiO₂ and SnO₂ was measured using temperature programmed reaction (TPR) in combination with mass spectroscopy (MS) at realistic reaction conditions of pressure and temperature. CO oxidation was performed in a gas mixture containing 0.025% CO and 0.025% O₂, diluted in helium at a constant total pressure of 1.1 bar, resulting in partial pressures of 0.27 mbar for each reactant. The obtained data were evaluated for each temperature and normalized to the number of Pt atoms present in each catalyst and are reported in Figure 2. In the case of Pt_{*n*} supported on SnO₂, the activity for Pt₄₀ starts at *T* = 250 °C with the rate of CO₂ production of 0.03 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹, whereas Pt₁₃ showed no activity at this temperature. At 300 °C, both cluster sizes revealed catalytic activity

with similar reaction rates of 0.1 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹. At the highest temperature of 350 °C, the rate of CO₂ production for Pt₄₀ clusters reached 2.1 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹, which was 15% higher than the rate measured for Pt₁₃ of 1.8 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹. CO₂ was the only product formed, turning over 14% and 16% of the fed CO for Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀, respectively, at the highest temperature.

Similar trends were observed for Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ clusters on the TiO₂ support, but with considerably higher reaction rates. Hence, at *T* = 250 °C, the rate of CO₂ production for Pt₄₀/TiO₂ reached 0.2 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹ and increased to 7.0 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 300 °C, which already surpassed the highest rate observed for clusters on SnO₂ (2.1 molecules atom⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 350 °C) with the CO consumption of 53%. Pt₁₃ on TiO₂ showed lower performance in comparison with Pt₄₀/TiO₂, and the

FIGURE 2 | Performance of supported cluster in CO oxidation reaction (CO:O₂ = 1:1, with partial pressure 0.27 mbar for each reactant). The left panel shows the CO₂ formation rates as a function of temperature for: Pt₁₃/TiO₂, Pt₄₀/TiO₂, Pt₁₃/SnO₂, and Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalysts, while the right panel presents the corresponding CO consumption.

reaction rate at $T = 300^\circ\text{C}$ reached $0.42 \text{ molecules atom}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, that is still almost 4 times higher than for the same cluster on SnO₂. The rate for Pt₁₃ further increased up to $6.1 \text{ molecules atom}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 350°C , 3 times higher than on SnO₂, and CO consumption approached 46%. Interestingly, at $T = 350^\circ\text{C}$, the performance of Pt₄₀/TiO₂ remains constant. We have already observed such a trend in our preview works [33], where saturation in the maximum conversion at elevated temperatures was explained by the mass transfer limitation due to the relatively large volume of the reaction cell, a phenomenon that was well described elsewhere in the literature [34, 35]. It is important to mention that blank TiO₂ and blank SnO₂ showed no catalytic activity.

In summary, the highest activity was reached for Pt clusters on TiO₂ at 350°C , which was about 3 times higher than for the same conditions on SnO₂, highlighting two trends: the activity of the clusters increases with size, and clusters supported on TiO₂ are more active than those on SnO₂. These results are in good agreement with the findings by Beniya et al. [36], where it was shown that despite smaller clusters having generally more undercoordinated atoms, the activity of supported Pt clusters at this scale is strongly determined/affected by the cluster-support interaction which can reduce their affinity with oxygen, leading to decreased activity in CO oxidation. Thus, multilayered clusters such as Pt₄₀ can have a higher activity than smaller clusters such as Pt₁₃, where most of the atoms are at the interface with the TiO₂. As a matter of fact, TiO₂ was proposed to make supported particles more resistant to oxidation due to charge transfer [37] that can be more pronounced in the case of small size-selected clusters. A similar effect was observed for Pt₂₄ clusters on SiO₂, where prolonged O₂ exposure had no effect on the resulting Pt oxidation state [38]. On the other hand, Pt clusters on SnO₂ are expected to exhibit stronger bonding. Taking the above into account, we assume that Pt clusters deposited on TiO₂ are more likely to preserve higher metallicity, which may be an important factor in determining their resulting activity. To explore the relationship between oxidation state, cluster size, and catalytic activity of clusters on various supports, we conducted in situ NAP-XPS characterization. This approach represents a significant step toward bridging the pressure gap in catalytic studies of size-selected Pt clusters, as most existing XPS studies in the literature are limited to UHV conditions.

2.2 | NAP-XPS Characterization Under Reaction Conditions

NAP-XPS measurements were focused on the acquisition of Pt 4f core levels of the supported clusters to identify changes in the oxidation state under conditions that replicate the catalytic testing performed during TPR measurements in the reaction cell. In addition, at each temperature step, the chemical composition of the surface was monitored by measuring the Si 2p, O 1s, C 1s, and Ti 2p or Sn 3d core levels.

In Figure 3, the Pt 4f spectra are presented for the as-prepared Pt_n clusters on both TiO₂ and SnO₂ supports, acquired at room temperature (RT) and in an inert atmosphere of 2 mbar of He. All the Pt 4f spectra consist of characteristic doublet peaks with the spin-orbit splitting of 3.35 eV. For Pt clusters supported on TiO₂ (Figure 3a,b), the fitting analysis of the spectra of both cluster sizes revealed the presence of a single pair of asymmetric components, with Pt 4f_{7/2} binding energy (BE) positions at 71.8 and

FIGURE 3 | NAP-XPS spectra of Pt 4f core-levels acquired at room temperature and in an inert atmosphere of 2 mbar of He for as-prepared catalysts: (a) Pt₁₃/TiO₂; (b) Pt₄₀/TiO₂; (c) Pt₁₃/SnO₂, and (d) Pt₄₀/SnO₂. All samples were exposed to air before measurements. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity.

71.7 eV for Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀, respectively. This corresponds to approximately 0.8 and 0.7 eV shifts toward higher BE compared to bulk metallic Pt. This BE shift to higher values for clusters with a small number of atoms is a well-established trend for supported size-selected clusters caused by final state effects, which scale with a trend close to $n^{-1/3}$ (where n is the number of atoms in cluster) [12, 39, 40]. As recently highlighted by Perco et al. [38], several additional effects can contribute to the interpretation of XPS data of supported size-selected clusters, requiring additional consideration to discuss the oxidation state of the catalyst. In our specific case, charge transfer between clusters and the TiO₂ support may also contribute to the BE shift [41–43]. Indeed, in the work of Watanabe et al., which focused on an in situ study under UHV conditions for clusters of similar size (from Pt₂ to Pt₁₅, deposited on crystalline TiO₂), the Pt 4f_{7/2} peak position was observed between 72.0 and 71.6 eV, respectively [39]. Moreover, the state of the amorphous TiO₂ support prepared by ALD could further affect the XPS binding energies, introducing an additional shift of more than 0.2 eV given by structural inhomogeneity and/or oxygen vacancies [44, 45].

This is given by the fact that vacuum-annealed TiO₂ (110) has numerous O vacancies on the surface, and if the clusters are bound there, the electrons associated with these vacancies tend to shift the BE to lower values. Thus, we attribute the measured BEs to an intermediate Pt^{δ+} state, often used in literature to indicate partial oxidation [46], where the positive net charge in the cluster is attributed to charge transfer effects from the support, and only in minor extent to a limited amount of chemisorbed oxygen coming from the air exposure [38]. This interpretation is supported by the asymmetric shape of the Pt 4f components obtained from the fitting analysis, which is typically related to the density of state at the Fermi level and is an indicator of metallicity [47–49]. While small clusters do not possess a well-defined Fermi level, the observed asymmetry may reflect the quasi-continuous nature of their electronic states and the developing density of states near the highest occupied levels. This phenomenon enables electron–hole pair excitations during photoemission, which is indicative of emerging metallic character and the ability of valence electrons to screen the core hole.

Interestingly, a different situation occurs with Pt clusters supported on SnO₂ (Figure 3c,d), where the fitting analysis of Pt 4f spectra revealed the presence of two pairs of symmetric components shifted to much higher binding energies, suggesting a higher oxidation state compared to Pt clusters on TiO₂. For Pt₁₃/SnO₂ (Figure 3c), the first pair of components, which correspond to 90% of the total spectral weight, shows a Pt 4f_{7/2} BE of 73.0 eV. We associate this component with the oxidation state Pt²⁺ [50]. The second pair of components with a much lower contribution (10% of spectral weight) shows Pt 4f_{7/2} BE of 75.0 eV, which we identified as Pt⁴⁺ [37]. For Pt₄₀ deposited on SnO₂, the fit revealed a very similar Pt oxidation states, with the presence of Pt²⁺ and Pt⁴⁺ components with a Pt 4f_{7/2} BE of 72.5 and 74.5 eV, respectively, both 0.5 eV lower than those observed for the smaller Pt₁₃ cluster. This energy difference between Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ cannot be accounted solely for final state effects, which generally shift the BEs of smaller clusters to higher values; thus, we believe that the 3D nature of Pt₄₀ clusters and their layer-dependent interaction with the SnO₂ support contribute to this phenomenon [12, 39]. In general, the higher oxidation state of Pt clusters on SnO₂ aligns well with the fact that SnO₂ is less

reducible than TiO₂, which results in weaker electron donation from SnO₂, leading to the stabilization of Pt with higher oxidation states [51]. We will discuss the Pt oxidation states and their influence on the catalytic performance in more detail in the discussion section below. It is also important to mention that, at this stage, the as-made catalysts contained a substantial amount of carbon, which we associate with the adsorbed carbonaceous species during the exposure to ambient air.

At the next step, the evolution of the chemical composition of clusters was studied under CO oxidation conditions replicating those used for the catalytic tests. The measurements were conducted in a gas mixture of CO and O₂ with the ratio 1:1, balanced in He, and a total pressure of 2 mbar (partial pressures of CO and O₂ were 0.05 mbar each).

In Figure 4, Pt 4f spectra are presented for Pt_n on TiO₂, measured in the temperature range from 50°C to 350°C with 100°C steps. Both Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ exhibit consistent behavior in the evolution of their oxidation states with temperature increases, showing a trend toward Pt reduction. First, at RT and under the gas mixture, both cluster sizes remained in the Pt^{δ+} state with the Pt 4f_{7/2} BE position of 71.8 eV, similar to the one measured in the inert atmosphere. At 150°C, a shift of 0.15 eV toward lower binding energies occurs for Pt₁₃/TiO₂, with Pt 4f_{7/2} BE = 71.7 eV. This can be attributed to Pt transition to metallic Pt⁰ state, which coincides well with already mentioned results reported by Watanabe, where metallic Pt₁₃ clusters on TiO₂ deposited and measured in UHV had a BE position of 71.6 eV [39], as well as with additional UHV experiments with Pt clusters measured in situ on different supports [52–54]. Interestingly, Pt₄₀/TiO₂ undergoes this transition only at the next temperature step of 250°C, suggesting that larger 3D clusters require higher temperatures to achieve the same level of reduction. Subsequently, another shift in Pt 4f occurs at the highest temperature of 350°C, where the peak position of Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ clusters shifted to slightly lower BE, 71.3 and 71.4 eV, respectively.

During all the steps of the experiment, the two Pt clusters show consistently different BEs, and even at high temperatures, the

FIGURE 4 | Evolution of the Pt 4f spectra with temperature ramping from 50°C to 350°C, acquired in situ during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/TiO₂ and (b) Pt₄₀/TiO₂. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at a pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity.

final BE is considerably higher than for bulk Pt (Pt bulk has BE = 70.9–71.2 eV [55], thin Pt layers have BE = 71.0 eV [56], nanoparticles with a size of 2 nm have BE = 71.2 eV [57]). This fact indicates that the size selection of the clusters within this temperature range is preserved, and the agglomeration is either absent or limited, i.e., clusters exhibit sintering resistance. Notably, XPS spectra revealed the sharpening of the Pt 4f peaks with increasing temperature. This suggests that the initial state comprised a broader distribution of cluster-support interactions, which became more uniform at temperatures of 150°C and above, due to more homogeneous clusters' confinement on the support surface, as well as surface cleaning from the adsorbed carbonaceous species at elevated temperatures.

In situ Pt 4f spectra acquired for Pt_n/SnO₂ under CO oxidation conditions at different temperatures are presented in Figure 5. As discussed above, initially (at RT in He atmosphere), Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ on SnO₂ pose similar Pt oxidation states with the presence of Pt²⁺ (90%) and Pt⁴⁺ (10%) components. Given the observed similarities in the oxidation states of both clusters, which agree with the very similar activity shown in Figure 2, we opted for slightly different approaches to study these samples. Specifically, Pt₁₃/SnO₂ was examined under the standard measurement sequence, similar to that used for Pt catalysts supported on TiO₂, while Pt₄₀/SnO₂ was prereduced in 2 mbar of 10% H₂ in He at 300°C to ensure a thorough verification of the final metallic state of platinum, which can also offer deeper insight into its reduction behavior and stability. Thus, starting with Pt₁₃/SnO₂ (see Figure 5a), we observed significant changes in the Pt oxidation state, showing a trend toward cluster reduction with each temperature step. The first changes in the spectrum can be observed already at 50°C, where the Pt⁴⁺ component with a Pt 4f_{7/2} BE of 75.0 eV almost completely vanishes, leaving the clusters predominantly in the oxidation state Pt²⁺ (BE = 73 eV). At 150°C, a new component appears at 72 eV, which can be attributed to the transitional Pt^{δ+} state with a total spectral weight of ~55%. At the next temperature step of 250°C, the reduction

process evolves further, with the Pt²⁺ component decreasing to less than 10% of the total spectrum weight, leaving the clusters mainly in Pt^{δ+} state. Finally, at 350°C, the fit revealed the presence of only one component with the BE position of 71.5 eV, which can be attributed to metallic Pt⁰.

In the case of Pt₄₀/SnO₂ (Figure 5b), prereduction of the sample in H₂ at 300°C resulted in a Pt 4f_{7/2} BE position at 71.7 eV, which shifted by approximately 0.7 eV to higher BE at RT. Under these reducing conditions, Pt is expected to transition to the metallic state, but considering significant shift in BE, we assigned this peak to Pt^{δ+} to emphasize the strong interaction with the SnO₂ support. This shift in BE also indirectly indicates that the size selection of the clusters is preserved even in a highly reducing environment. The subsequent addition of CO and O₂ gases at RT did not affect the formal oxidation state of Pt. With the temperature increase, the position of Pt 4f_{7/2} showed an overall trend toward lower BEs reaching 71.6 eV at 250°C (assigned to Pt^{δ+}) and finally 71.4 eV at 350°C (assigned to Pt⁰). Similar to titania-supported catalysts, as well as Pt₁₃/SnO₂, this indicates that clusters remain chemically and structurally stable, although minor agglomeration cannot be completely excluded. The study by Steinhauer et al. can further support this conclusion, where nonselected Pt particles smaller than 2 nm deposited on SnO₂ demonstrated that Pt particles did not migrate or ripen during the in situ heating up to 350°C (in 20 mbar O₂) [58] confirming the stability of Pt on SnO₂ at this temperature range. A slight deviation (0.2–0.3 eV) from the 71.6 eV position reported in the literature for metallic clusters can be attributed to the temperature effect, which will be discussed and experimentally confirmed below for Pt₁₃/SnO₂ catalysts.

In addition, we performed the analysis of Ti 2p and Sn 3d spectra that confirmed high chemical stability of supporting materials throughout all the measured conditions. The Ti 2p spectra (Figure S3) revealed that titania was in TiO₂ state for both catalysts, with Ti 2p_{3/2} peak appearing at approximately 458.7 eV. Similarly, Sn 3d_{5/2} peak measured for Pt_n/SnO₂ catalysts had a BE of 486.7 eV corresponding to SnO₂ (see Figure S4). Importantly, with the temperature increase, we were able to observe the surface cleaning from adsorbed carbonaceous species (see C 1s spectra in Figure S5), with the carbon content decreasing to ~3 at.% for all the catalysts except Pt₄₀/SnO₂ where carbon content was ~6 at.%. The C 1s peak totally vanishes at 450°C, as evidenced by our subsequent stability tests reported below. Latter also demonstrates that coking, which often leads to poisoning and deactivation of the catalysts, can be excluded under our reaction conditions. It is important to note that the substantial amount of adsorbed carbon observed at lower temperatures can inhibit active sites and lead to reduced catalytic activity, as reported elsewhere [33]. Also, most of the C 1s signal is expected to come from adsorbants on the support rather than on the clusters due to the low Pt coverage; therefore, a more precise analysis is not possible with our spectral resolution.

FIGURE 5 | Evolution of the Pt 4f spectra with temperature ramping from 50°C to 350°C, acquired in situ during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/SnO₂ and (b) Pt₄₀/SnO₂. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at a pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. Note: after the initial measurements at RT, Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalyst was prereduced in 2 mbar of H₂ at 300°C. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity.

2.3 | Chemical Stability Under Harsh Conditions

To further investigate the chemical stability of the supported cluster-based catalysts, we conducted an additional set of NAP-XPS measurements with higher O₂ concentrations that also included the additional temperature step at 450°C. In Figure 6,

FIGURE 6 | The evolution of the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ peak position during the stability tests for Pt_n clusters on TiO_2 and SnO_2 supports shown for 3 consecutive temperature ramps up to $450^\circ C$ and $CO:O_2$ ratio: 1:1 for 1st ramp, 1:4 for 2nd ramp, and 1:9 for 3rd ramp. The ratios correspond to constant CO concentration of 2.5% (partial pressure of 0.05 mbar), and different O_2 concentrations of 2.5%, 10%, and 22.5% (partial pressures of 0.05, 0.25, and 0.45 mbar, respectively). The data points are further highlighted according to the assigned oxidation state of platinum. In the case of SnO_2 support, Pt $4f_{7/2}$ contains two components during the 1st ramp that are shown as peak 1 and peak 2 in the legend. The binding energies were referenced to the position of Si $2p_{3/2}$ core level of Si–Si bond, with an estimated accuracy of ± 0.1 eV.

the evolution of the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ BE is presented for 3 consecutive temperature ramps with $CO:O_2$ ratio: 1:1; 1:4, and 1:9, respectively. These ratios correspond to constant CO concentration of 2.5% (partial pressure of 0.05 mbar), while the O_2 concentrations were 2.5%, 10%, and 22.5%, corresponding to partial pressures of 0.05, 0.25 and 0.45 mbar, respectively. Hence, continuing NAP-XPS measurements with the previously used reaction conditions of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O_2 , but at an elevated temperature of $450^\circ C$, BEs for both cluster sizes on TiO_2 are further shifted by 0.3 eV toward lower energies relative to those recorded at $350^\circ C$, with a Pt $4f_{7/2}$ binding energy of 71.0 eV. This BE corresponds to bulk metallic platinum, suggesting that at this elevated temperature the clusters agglomerate on titania support. Indeed, at this temperature, enhanced mobility can lead to Pt clusters' migration on the titania surface [59].

Subsequent measurements at higher O_2 concentrations of 10% and 22.5% showed no significant changes in the chemical composition, with Pt clusters remaining in the bulk metallic state. At this point, it is important to mention that at $450^\circ C$, traces of Cu contamination (coming from gas inlet Cu tube at the NAP-XPS setup) were detected on both Pt/ TiO_2 catalysts. Nevertheless, based on the Pt 4f spectra before and after contamination occurred, these small traces of Cu do not affect the resulting oxidation state of Pt.

In contrast to titania-supported catalysts, both Pt_{13} and Pt_{40} on SnO_2 demonstrated high stability at an elevated temperature of $450^\circ C$, with Pt $4f_{7/2}$ BE remaining unchanged at 71.3 eV, indicating that the clusters retained their stability without agglomeration. Furthermore, after initiating a second temperature ramp with 10% O_2 concentration, the Pt $4f_{7/2}$ BE measured at $50^\circ C$ was observed at 71.5 eV, representing 0.2 eV shift to higher BE. With increasing temperature, the BE gradually shifted to 71.3 eV at $450^\circ C$. This behavior/cycle repeated during the subsequent measurements of the third temperature ramp with 22.5%

O_2 concentration. Such temperature-induced shifts in BE are likely attributed to changes in charge transfer between clusters and support, and/or adsorption/desorption of O_2 and CO. Moreover, under an atmosphere of 20% O_2 in He (without CO) at $300^\circ C$, the clusters on SnO_2 were chemically stable and remained in their metallic state. These results confirm that Pt clusters on SnO_2 exhibit significant sintering resistance even under harsh reaction conditions of high O_2 concentrations and elevated temperatures. The resistance of Pt clusters to oxidation was also confirmed by Anderson et al., who found that Pt_2 and Pt_{24} clusters supported on SiO_2 , after exposure to a large dose of O_2 /air, did not reveal any significant BE shift, even though ISS measurements confirmed the deposition of O atoms on the cluster surface [38]. In summary, our results show that the nature of the support has a significant influence on the stability of Pt clusters. While TiO_2 -supported clusters tend to agglomerate at elevated temperatures, SnO_2 -supported clusters demonstrate superior sintering resistance and chemical stability. This highlights the importance of support selection in designing stable and efficient cluster-based catalysts.

3 | Discussions

3.1 | Support Influence on Pt Oxidation State and on Activity

The oxidation state of Pt for the as-made catalysts is of particular interest, as clusters can display unique behavior compared to their bulk forms. Starting from the clusters supported on SnO_2 , the initial oxidation is attributed to the exposure to ambient air during transport from the cluster deposition source to the NAP-XPS instrument, enhanced by the strong metal–support interaction (SMSI) [60]. However, the high abundance of Pt^{2+} is in contrast with the typical behavior of bulk Pt, with the bulk oxide phase PtO being thermodynamically unstable, differently from the more common PtO_2 [61]. This result underscores the unique characteristics of the clusters with respect to their bulk counterparts and aligns with theoretical studies on the formation energy per atom for Pt_nO_n and Pt_nO_{2n} clusters, which predicted that their oxidation follows the sequence $Pt_n \rightarrow Pt_nO_n \rightarrow Pt_nO_{1.5n} \rightarrow Pt_nO_{2n}$ [62, 63]. This coincides well with the experimental study, where Pt_{10} clusters supported on Al_2O_3 (also in this case exposed to air) were reported to possess a mixture of oxidation states dominated by the metallic one, accounting for approximately 60%, with the remaining 40% similarly divided between Pt^{2+} and Pt^{4+} [64]. This behavior is reminiscent of the formation of PtO_x on F-doped SnO_2 (FTO) substrates, a phenomenon that is relevant in the catalyst preparation for Grätzel-type solar cells [65].

As already discussed, in terms of size effect, Pt_{40} on SnO_2 showed very similar Pt oxidation states to Pt_{13}/SnO_2 with two components assigned to Pt^{2+} and Pt^{4+} , but with a Pt $4f_{7/2}$ core level shift of ~ 0.5 eV to lower BEs. This difference could have to do with the fact that larger clusters possess a lower percentage of atoms at the cluster-support interface, which are more inclined to exhibit cationic character [36, 66], resulting in a lower net charge and average oxidation state of the larger clusters. On the other hand, the different Pt behavior on TiO_2 with only the $Pt^{\delta+}$ intermediate oxidation state may stem from the anticipated charge transfer from the TiO_2 support to the Pt particles [41]. This phenomenon, referred to as the “Schwab effect” [42], occurs when a metal oxide

semiconductor support influences deposited particles through charge transfer, which can also facilitate the dissociation of CO molecules [43]. Similarly, recent calculations for Pt_m ($m \in [2, 8]$) have shown that when supported on TiO₂, cluster oxidation is hindered compared to free clusters in the gas phase [62].

Next, considering the Pt oxidation state under the conditions that maximize catalytic activity at 350°C, NAP-XPS results indicate that metallic Pt serves as the active phase facilitating CO oxidation on both TiO₂ and SnO₂ [67]. Despite these similarities, we observe a significant difference in the resulting catalytic performance (Figure 2), with Pt clusters on TiO₂ outperforming those on SnO₂. This behavior cannot be unambiguously explained by the Pt chemistry, as all catalysts exhibit the same ~ 0.3 eV shift to higher Pt BE compared to bulk references. While core electrons are not directly involved in bond formation, their binding energies can indirectly reflect changes in the valence electronic structure, which might not always be directly measurable, for example, in cases of electron transfer during the SMSI and related size-dependent rehybridization of metal orbitals [68]. Therefore, we suggest that the difference in the catalytic activity arises from variations in the electronic interaction between the clusters and their corresponding supports, which can influence the valence band (VB) stability and, consequently, the surface's ability to bind reactants (CO and O₂) [12]. This phenomenon is well described in terms of the d-band model and Sabatier's principle [69]. Hence, achieving the optimal balance of metal-support interaction, as observed for Pt₄₀/TiO₂, promotes efficient CO chemisorption and the dissociative adsorption of O₂, ultimately leading to CO₂ production via a Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism [70, 71].

In contrast to TiO₂, it is expected that SnO₂ interacts more strongly with Pt than TiO₂ in terms of bond formation [31]. This interaction is facilitated by the relative position of SnO₂'s Fermi level as well as its work function increasing with temperature, which promotes charge transfer and stabilizes oxidized states of Pt through covalent or ionic bonding [32, 72]. The latter can explain greater chemical stability and resistance to sintering for Pt clusters on SnO₂, as we observed in Figure 6, though this stability comes at the expense of reduced catalytic activity [72]. We will address this in more detail in the last section below, where SnO₂ overgrowth will be considered as one of the factors as well.

In terms of size effect of clusters, which is shown to be crucial in the case of both substrates, the larger Pt₄₀ clusters exhibit higher activity compared to Pt₁₃. While CO oxidation is not typically considered a structure-sensitive reaction, it was already proven that the catalytic reactivity as a function of size correlates with the position of the d-band center, which may affect the ability of activate O₂ species [69, 73–75]. For smaller clusters, such as Pt₁₃, the reduced performance may be attributed to a particularly stable valence electronic structure, which may also be manifested in slightly higher BE we observed [12]. As a matter of fact, these smaller clusters have a higher percentage of Pt atoms located at the cluster-support interface, which are significantly influenced by electron transfer from the support than atoms in the upper layers of larger 3D clusters [36]. These may limit the efficiency of O₂ dissociation for efficient CO oxidation. Previous findings within a similar size range further support the relationship between electronic structure and reactivity, highlighting the critical role of the particle shape [12, 76].

In addition, the diffusion and migration rates of adsorbed CO and O species on the Pt clusters are expected to follow a similar size-dependent trend. Larger Pt₄₀ clusters, with extended Pt–Pt ensembles, likely facilitate surface diffusion of CO and O due to weaker local adsorption energies and lower diffusion barriers. In contrast, the smaller Pt₁₃ clusters, which are more strongly coupled to the support and electronically perturbed by charge transfer, may exhibit more localized adsorption sites and reduced surface mobility of reactants. Such reduced diffusivity can hinder the recombination of adsorbed CO and O species into CO₂, further contributing to the lower apparent activity of smaller clusters.

Moreover, the oxide support strongly modulates charge transfer and the degree of metal-support interaction. On more oxophilic supports such as SnO₂, partial electron transfer from the metal to the support can increase the metal's positive character, strengthening O adsorption and suppressing CO mobility. Meanwhile, less oxophilic supports such as TiO₂ provide weaker anchoring and less charge redistribution, allowing adsorbates to diffuse more freely. Additionally, support-mediated adsorption effects may contribute to the observed trends, although a detailed investigation of this phenomenon is beyond the scope of this work [77, 78].

3.2 | Ex Situ XPS and Ion Scattering Spectroscopy on Pt₄₀/SnO₂

An additional comparison between the clusters on the two supports is presented in Figure 7a with an overlay of Pt 4f spectra for Pt₄₀ on TiO₂ and SnO₂. It follows that the spectra for Pt on SnO₂ exhibit a lower degree of asymmetry while maintaining the same BE position assigned to metallic Pt. Such an alteration in the spectra's symmetry suggests that SnO₂ induces a more uniform electronic interaction with the Pt clusters, suppressing the intrinsic asymmetry of metallic Pt by either altering the density of states around the Fermi level or modifying the relaxation dynamics during XPS measurements [79].

Thus, such behavior could be attributed to the strong metal-support interaction between Pt and SnO₂, and associated charge transfer. On the other hand, under certain temperature conditions, SnO₂ can migrate over the metal clusters leading to partial overgrowth or complete encapsulation of the clusters, which can also alter their electronic and geometric properties, affecting how electrons respond during XPS measurement. To further investigate this phenomenon in relation to SMSI and potential overgrowth, we conducted additional surface characterization using ex situ XPS in conjunction with ion scattering spectroscopy (ISS). XPS primarily provides information from the top ~ 3 nm of the surface (accounting for $\sim 90\%$ of the detected signal), whereas ISS is highly surface-sensitive, probing only the outermost atomic layer. The combination of these two techniques can help to understand the origin of the lower asymmetry observed for SnO₂. Consequently, in Figure 7b,c, Pt 4f spectra are presented for 3 different Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalysts, as follows: (i) after the TPR catalytic test at atmospheric pressure, (ii) after the NAP-XPS measurements in the low mbar pressure range, and (iii) pristine (as-deposited). All samples were exposed to ambient air during transportation prior to the measurements. It can be seen in Figure 7b that the sample reduced during the NAP-XPS experimental conditions re-oxidizes upon exposure to air, showing a very similar Pt oxidation state to that observed for the sample

FIGURE 7 | (a) Comparison of Pt 4f spectra acquired for Pt₄₀ clusters on TiO₂ and SnO₂ at 350°C and CO oxidation conditions; Pt 4f spectra measured in UHV conditions before (b) and after (c) sputtering (normalized to the same intensity) for 3 different Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalysts: 1—after catalytic test at TPR, 2—after NAP-XPS measurements, and 3—pristine (as-deposited); (d) relative ratios of Pt and Sn calculated as intensity of the element after sputtering divided by the intensity before sputtering based on XPS measurements in UHV; (e) ISS spectra before (top) and after (bottom) sputtering; (f) relative abundance ratio of Sn to Pt (Sn/Pt ratio after sputtering divided by Sn/Pt ratio before sputtering) obtained from XPS and ISS, respectively. A standard uncertainty of ±10% was assumed for the XPS/ISS-derived ratios, reflecting the typical experimental/fitting precision of these techniques.

after TPR measurements with the presence of Pt⁰ and Pt²⁺. The pristine sample stands apart, exhibiting the highest level of oxidation with only Pt²⁺ and Pt⁴⁺ components, that is consistent with previous measurements reported in Figure 3. These observations also manifested in the initial amount of carbonaceous species on the surface, with the as-deposited sample containing the highest carbon content (see Table S1). To remove these surface adsorbates, while preserving the catalyst surface, gentle ion sputtering/etching with He⁺ was performed, decreasing the surface carbon content to the level observed during NAP-XPS measurements at 350°C, which also corresponds to the conditions with the highest catalytic activity. Comparing the Pt and Sn contents before and after etching, in Figure 7d, we can observe an increase in intensity for both elements, with Sn becoming significantly more exposed. This confirms that sputtering leads to surface cleaning only, with Pt losses considered negligible. Importantly, as can be seen in Figure 7c, ion etching also led to Pt reduction with the Pt 4f spectra maintaining low asymmetry, showing a similar surface chemistry as observed in NAP-XPS.

In a similar manner, ISS spectra were measured before and after sputtering as shown in Figure 7e (obtained by He⁺ scattering from individual atoms in the surface layer, with the energy of the scattered He⁺ determining the mass of the surface atom) [80, 81]. The peaks with kinetic energies of ~855 and ~895 eV were assigned to Sn and Pt, respectively. To compare trends observed in ISS (sensitive to the first layer) and XPS (sensitive to ~3–5 nm), we introduced a relative abundance ratio *k*, defined as the Sn/Pt ratio after sputtering divided by the Sn/Pt ratio before sputtering, as depicted in Figure 7f. The latter indicates how the

Sn/Pt ratio evolves in dependence on the probing depth of these two complementary techniques with *k* > 1 directly related to the increase in Sn content. For XPS, samples measured after TPR and NAP-XPS had roughly the same relative abundance with *k* slightly above 1, suggesting a minor rise in the overall Sn/Pt ratio. In contrast, ISS revealed a much larger increase in *k* of approximately 100% and 50% for the NAP and TPR samples, respectively, indicating significant enrichment of the outermost layer with Sn after surface cleaning from carbonaceous species. These results can indicate partial Sn overgrowth, where some of the Pt atoms in the cluster are covered by SnO₂.

This observation can be rationalized by the higher oxophilicity of Sn (relative to Ti and Pt) and the resulting interfacial chemistry, which under our oxidative conditions can further favor the formation and migration of SnO_x species [29]. The greater oxophilicity of SnO₂ also increases the adhesion energy of Pt clusters to the support, promoting stronger anchoring and reduced cluster mobility [82]. This is consistent with our NAP-XPS measurements, which show no distinct oxidized Pt states (the Pt 4f peak remains characteristic of metallic Pt with only a small positive BE shift), while the Sn 3d spectra are consistent with near-stoichiometric SnO₂. Taken together, these data indicate SMSI behavior driven by partial charge transfer from Pt to SnO_x, accompanied by physical encapsulation/overgrowth rather than by formation of bulk Pt-Sn metallic bonds or significant Pt oxidation.

It is also important to note that overgrowth formation can strongly depend on various factors, such as the reaction environment and particle size. Recent studies have demonstrated that

the redox gas composition can remove or re-establish oxide overlayers in the Pt/TiO₂ system at pressures around 1 bar, as confirmed by in situ HRTEM analysis [83, 84]. Meanwhile, the SMSI-induced overgrowth in similar TiO₂-supported systems was shown to depend on cluster size, as evidenced by XPS and ISS measurements [85, 86]. These dynamic and size-dependent effects are therefore consistent with our observations of the catalytic performance of Pt clusters supported on SnO₂ and TiO₂.

The as-deposited sample exhibited the same trend but with even greater changes in relative abundance, which can be attributed to a much higher initial level of adsorbed carbonaceous species. Based on these observations, we can also conclude that the lower mbar pressure used in NAP-XPS is sufficient to understand the evolution of the catalyst chemistry occurring under atmospheric pressure during the catalytic CO oxidation at TPR (does not need to be valid for other, more complex reactions), as evidenced by the similarity in trends for these two samples observed in this combined XPS/ISS investigation.

To summarize, since the BEs are directly linked to the charge in the atoms composing the clusters, where higher BEs indicate a higher positive charge [87], it can be deduced that the activity increases as the charge in the clusters decreases. However, the resulting catalytic activity is not solely defined by the final chemical state of Pt, but rather evolves from the combination of factors, including metal support interaction and the size-dependent nature of the clusters. In this context, our findings underscore the effect of SMSI, particularly in the case of SnO₂ support, where SnO₂ overgrowth is suggested to be responsible for the enhanced chemical stability, as well as sintering resistance, observed by NAP-XPS. This, in turn, can limit access to the active Pt sites, leading to reduced CO adsorption and oxygen activation, ultimately resulting in the lower catalytic activity of Pt_n/SnO₂ compared to TiO₂ based catalysts.

4 | Conclusion

Size selected Pt_n ($n = 13, 40$) clusters supported on ALD-grown metal oxides demonstrate catalytic activity influenced by the choice of support, with TiO₂-supported clusters exhibiting nearly double the reaction rates compared to those supported on SnO₂, and by size, with larger Pt₄₀ clusters performing better than Pt₁₃ on the same substrates. In situ NAP-XPS measurements highlighted major differences for the clusters supported on the two oxides already at room temperatures, where it was shown that Pt on TiO₂ remains in a metallic and Pt^{δ+} state, whereas SnO₂ is present as a combination of Pt²⁺ and Pt⁴⁺. For increasing temperature in an atmosphere of CO and O₂, all clusters were reduced to metallic Pt. While Pt_n/TiO₂ consistently exhibits slightly lower BE than clusters on SnO₂. Final shifts in BE at 350°C in comparison to bulk value were +0.3 and +0.4 eV for Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ on TiO₂, respectively, and +0.4 and +0.5 eV for Pt₁₃ and Pt₄₀ on SnO₂, respectively. As a result, the catalytic activity in CO oxidation is primarily determined by the cluster size and their interaction with the support, particularly due to charge transfer effects. Interestingly, Pt 4f spectrum for TiO₂ and SnO₂ shows different asymmetry, which also indicates different interactions between cluster and support. Furthermore, stability tests confirmed that Pt clusters on TiO₂ undergo partial agglomeration at 450°C, while those on SnO₂ remained stable. Even when

exposed to an O₂-rich atmosphere at 300°C without CO, the clusters retain their metallic character. Ex situ XPS and ISS measurements on used catalysts further highlight the role of strong metal–support interactions, particularly in the case of SnO₂, where overgrowth contributed to enhanced chemical stability and sintering resistance. However, this overgrowth also reduced the availability of active Pt sites, limiting CO adsorption and oxygen activation, ultimately leading to lower catalytic activity compared to TiO₂-supported clusters. The consistency in trends between NAP-XPS and TPR results suggests that lower-pressure NAP-XPS provides relevant insights into catalyst evolution under reaction conditions.

These findings provide a deeper understanding of the catalytic processes occurring on the surface of the studied systems and offer valuable guidance for the design of new, more efficient catalysts, where both activity and stability can be optimized through SMSI adjustments, for example, by implementing mixed-oxide supports that could enable tunable control of the electronic and structural properties at the cluster-support interface.

5 | Methods

5.1 | ALD

As a support material, the surface of naturally oxidized N-type phosphorus-doped silicon chips (Si [100]) from University Wafers with 675 μm thickness and with a ~2 nm thick native oxide top layer was coated with thin layers of TiO₂ and SnO₂ by atomic layer deposition (ALD).

The SnO₂ and TiO₂ films were prepared in an R-200 standard reactor (Picosun) The 1.5 nm thick SnO₂ film was fabricated by alternating pulses of tetrakis(dimethylamido)tin(IV) (TDMASn, STREM Chemicals) and H₂O (EpiValence) precursors and by 16 cycles consisting of a pulse-purge sequence: 1.6 s pulse TDMASn – 6 s N₂ purge – 0.1 s pulse of H₂O – 9 s N₂ purge. The stainless steel bubbler with TDMASn was maintained at 65°C and 22°C for H₂O. The reaction chamber temperature was set to 118°C, and the pressure was 7 mbar during deposition.

The 1.5-nm-thick TiO₂ film was fabricated by alternating pulses of tetrakis(dimethylamido)titanium(IV) (TDMATi from Strem Chemicals) and water (EpiValence) precursors and by 26 cycles consisting of a pulse-purge sequence: 1.6 s TDMATi, 6 s N₂ purge, 0.1 s H₂O, 8 s N₂. The TDMATi was evaporated at 85°C. The substrate temperature was 150°C and the pressure was 10 mbar during the deposition. Ultrahigh-purity nitrogen (Messer Technogas, 99.999%) was used as a carrier and purging gas of the ALD apparatus. The thickness of the ALD oxide layers was measured by ellipsometry.

5.2 | AFM (Atomic Force Microscopy)

The nanomorphology of the supports was characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM, Dimension Icon, Bruker) in semicontact (tapping) mode. A silicon cantilever (VTESPA-300) with a resonant frequency, f_{res} , of approximately 300 kHz, a spring constant, k , of 42 N m⁻¹, and a nominal tip radius of 5 nm (Bruker) was employed. The Gwyddion software (v. 2.53) was used for processing AFM image data and for the calculation of the roughness (R_a).

5.3 | Cluster Deposition

The synthesis of atomically precise Pt_n ($n = 13, 40$) clusters was performed using molecular beams in the gas phase, utilizing a vacuum apparatus. The instrument consists of three interconnected vacuum chambers differentially pumped with turbomolecular pumps backed with fore-vacuum rotary pumps. The charged clusters were produced in the first chamber by means of a magnetron-based sputter source with a liquid nitrogen-cooled gas aggregation chamber of the Haberland type [88] powered by an Advanced Energy model MDX 500 DC Power Supply. Argon and helium were used as the sputtering and carrier gases, respectively, with a typical total flow in the range of 350–500 sccm. For catalyst preparation: a 2-in. diameter Pt sputter target was used in cluster source to produce Pt_{13} and Pt_{40} . To avoid redundancy, we use the notation Pt_n in contexts where the discussion is general to both cluster sizes, whereas the specific labels Pt_{13} and Pt_{40} are used only when referring to one size explicitly. The beam of positively charged clusters produced in the source chamber was directed onto the entrance orifice of the ion guide chamber and was collected and guided downstream into two differentially pumped chambers by a series of conical and linear octupoles. Then, the molecular beam containing a distribution of cluster sizes entered the mass spectrometer and the output of the apparatus was optimized for the desired cluster size by online monitoring of the mass spectrum of the clusters produced (for typical mass spectra of the produced Pt clusters used for the deposition of clusters, see Figure S1). Next, the desired single size clusters were filtered out by the mass spectrometer and directed toward the support in the deposition chamber. The flux of charged clusters landing on the support was measured in real-time using a picoammeter (Keithley 6487), which was also used to bias the substrate to control the impact energy of the clusters during their landing on the support, keeping their kinetic energy below 1 eV per metal atom. Under such low-energy deposition conditions, the kinetic energy is too low to cause fragmentation of the clusters or penetration into the support. Instead, their final structure on the surface is largely determined by the metal-support interaction, as the binding energy between the cluster and the oxide surface can still induce partial structural relaxation during equilibration. Using custom homemade software, written in Python, the deposition current was converted on-line into the total charge, providing the number of clusters (and atoms) deposited, as well as the atomic monolayer equivalent surface coverage. Typical deposition currents were in the range of a few nA, corresponding to a flux of clusters landing on the surface at a rate in the order of 10^{10} clusters per second with the spot size approximately 12 mm in diameter (corresponding to an area of 1.13 cm² per spot) and Gaussian distribution on the surface. Cluster were deposited in the soft-landing regime ($E_{kin} < 1$ eV/atom) onto Si chips 22 × 20 mm coated with two different support materials: TiO₂ or SnO₂ prepared by ALD as already discussed above. The coverage was kept at 10% of the atomic monolayer equivalent (ML) for samples prepared for catalytic tests, which is equal to 55 ng of Pt or 1.3×10^{14} atoms of Pt. A detailed description of the cluster synthesis process can be found elsewhere [15]. After deposition, the samples were transferred under air into the test setup. For NAP-XPS, XPS and ISS samples were deposited on smaller chips 10 × 10 mm, based on the sample holder in the XPS machine. The deposited spot was 0.64 cm² with 10% ML for Pt_{13} and 20% ML for Pt_{40} , with two extra samples of Pt_{40}

on SnO₂ deposited also with 10% ML, for relevant comparison at ex situ XPS and ISS. For the deposition for TEM measurement, the TEM grid was held in the aluminum envelope, and 0.1% ML was deposited.

5.4 | Catalytic Testing

The tests were performed in a custom reaction cell made of aluminum alloy (EN AW 6061) with an internal volume of 33 cm³ under continuous flow (20.0 sccm) of a reactant mixture containing 0.025% CO and 0.025% O₂ seeded in helium at a constant pressure of 1.1 bar, resulting in partial pressures of 0.27 mbar for each reactant. The mixing of reactant gases was realized in a custom mixer setup equipped with mass-flow controllers (MFCs) (Brooks SLA5850). The pressure in the reaction cell was monitored using a pressure transducer (Omega PX209) and kept at a constant pre-set pressure by a downstream mass-flow controller (Brooks SLA5850) integrated into a regulation loop pumped by a diaphragm pump (Divac 1.4HV3) and controlled by a custom homemade software written in Python. The investigated sample was heated on a boron nitride heater (Momentive Performance Materials Inc.), using a Kepco power supply, with the temperature ramp set and regulated using a LakeShore 340 controller in combination with a K-type thermocouple attached to the body of the heater plate. The walls of the reaction cell were cooled by water circulating through it at a temperature of 20°C maintained by an external chiller (Thermo AC200). Prior to the experiment, the temperature on the sample surface was calibrated against the temperature of the body of the heater using a second K-type thermocouple in contact with the surface of a blank silicon chip under the same flow of He as during catalyst testing. A mass spectrometer with an electron impact ionization source (Pfeiffer Vacuum PrismaPlus QMS 220) differentially pumped with a turbomolecular pumping station (Pfeiffer HiCube) was used for online analysis of the composition of gas leaving the reaction cell. The gas in between the outlet of the reaction cell and the downstream mass-flow controller was sampled into the differentially pumped mass spectrometer chamber using an electronic needle control valve (Pfeiffer EVR 116), with the flowrate controlled by a regulator (Pfeiffer RVC 300) combined with a pressure gauge (Pfeiffer PKR 261) to keep a constant pressure set to 5.0×10^{-6} mbar in the mass spectrometer chamber. The mass spectrometer chamber was pumped by a turbomolecular pump (Pfeiffer HiCube 80 Eco), which typically reached a background pressure of about 2×10^{-8} mbar. All upstream and downstream gas lines in the path from mixer MFCs to the reaction cell and downstream from the cell were heated to 70°C.

The mass spectrometer was operated in the continuous mass scanning mode (2 scans per minute) in the range from 5 to 50 *m/z* controlled by PV MassSpec software (Pfeiffer). The electron impact energy for the ionization was set to 70 eV. The sensitivity of the mass spectrometer for the desired molecules (CO, O₂, and CO₂) was determined using calibrated gas mixtures (certified analytical grade mixed gas, Messer). The uncertainty of the measured concentrations was estimated to be ~2%.

Before the catalytic test, and with the sample in the reactor, the reaction cell and all tubing were first evacuated and flushed several times with pure helium. Then, for 0.5 h, a constant flow of

helium (20 sccm) was maintained through the reaction cell at 1.1 bar and 25°C. After flushing with pure helium, the gas was switched to the reactant mixture (maintaining the 1066 mbar pressure and 20.0 sccm flow rate), and the sampling of the gas to the mass spectrometer started. The flow of the reactant mixture was kept for 4 h at 25°C for the sample to stabilize the background in the mass spectrometer before the start of the temperature ramp. The reactant mixture, consisting of 0.025% CO and 0.025% O₂ in helium (i.e., a 1:1 CO to O₂ molar ratio), was obtained by mixing 0.50 sccm of 1.0% CO in helium (Messer) with 0.50 sccm of 1.0% oxygen diluted in helium (Messer) and 19.00 sccm of pure He (Messer).

The performance of the catalysts was tested in a temperature range from 25°C to 350°C. The temperature program ramp consists of seven increasing temperature steps from 50°C to 350°C in increments of 50°C, followed by direct decreasing down to 50°C. Each temperature set point was approached with a ramp rate of 5°C min⁻¹ followed by a dwell time of 20 min at each temperature.

5.5 | NAP-XPS

Near-ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (NAP-XPS) measurements were conducted using a ProvenX NAP-XPS system (SPECs Surface Nano Analysis GmbH), equipped with a monochromatic Al K α X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.6$ eV) and a hemispherical energy analyzer. Survey spectra were acquired over a binding energy range of 1200–0 eV using a pass energy of 48.5 eV and a step size of 1 eV, with two spectra collected for improved accuracy. The measurement spot has a diameter of approximately 500 μ m. For each sample, the position was adjusted to the center of the measured area. High-resolution spectra of individual components were recorded with a reduced step size of 0.1 eV and a pass energy of 30 eV, and the final spectra were obtained by averaging 20 individual measurements. The analysis chamber allows for gas-phase environments up to 10 mbar while maintaining ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions in the electron analyzer region.

Samples (10 \times 10 mm²) were mounted on a stainless-steel sample plate and heated via an IR-laser heating system, enabling in situ heating up to 900°C. Temperature was monitored by a K-type thermocouple in direct contact with the sample surface. Before introducing the reaction gases, the base pressure was maintained at 10⁻⁸ mbar. The chamber was first filled with 2 mbar of He, and spectra were recorded in an inert atmosphere at room temperature. Subsequently, to study catalysts during the CO oxidation reaction, the gas mixture containing 2.5 vol% CO and 2.5 vol% O₂ diluted in He was introduced, corresponding to partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant and a total pressure 2 mbar. Measurements were then performed at 323, 423, 523, and 623 K.

For the stability test under the given reaction conditions with CO: O₂ ratio 1:1, temperature range was extended up to 723 K. After completing the measurements at 723 K, the samples were cooled to room temperature, and the procedure was repeated with two additional reaction mixtures containing increased amounts of oxygen: (i) 2.5 vol% CO and 10.0 vol% O₂ in He and (ii) 2.5 vol% CO and 22.5 vol% O₂ in He, corresponding to CO:O₂ ratios of 1:4 and 1:9, respectively. These correspond to constant CO partial pressure of 0.05 mbar, and O₂ partial pressures of 0.25 and 0.45 mbar, respectively.

Unlike all other samples, the Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalyst was studied using modified measurement sequence, which included H₂ pre-reduction to ensure a thorough verification of the final metallic state of platinum. For these needs, after spectra acquisition at room temperature in He, Pt₄₀/SnO₂ was reduced in 10% H₂ in He with total pressure 2 mbar at 573 K for 1 h, followed by XPS measurement.

5.6 | XPS Data Analysis

XPS spectra analysis was carried out using CasaXPS software. All binding energies for component analysis were referenced to the position of Si 2p_{3/2} core level of Si–Si bond, set at 99.2 eV (corresponds to Si 2p peak position of 99.4 eV). The exception are spectra for Pt₄₀/TiO₂, where BEs were calibrated to the Si 2s with peak position of 150.6 eV. In all cases, the fitting was performed using Shirley background and all core-level spectra (except for Pt 4f) were fitted using the symmetric LA (1.53,243) lineshape, which represents a Voigt profile (a convolution of Gaussian and Lorentzian distributions), and is a default option for symmetric fitting in CasaXPS. For certain spectral regions, the lineshape parameters were fine-tuned to get the lowest standard deviations of the residuals of the fit, for example, the Si 2s region was fitted using the Lorentzian Asymmetric (LA) (1.53,100) lineshape. The Pt 4f spectra were fitted using a combination of a symmetric Gaussian/Lorentzian (GL) product function for the Pt oxide components of the spectra and Lorentzian Asymmetric Lineshape, LA (1.3,3,100), for the Pt metal component, when both components were present. The characteristic spin-orbit splitting between Pt 4f_{7/2} and Pt 4f_{5/2} peaks was kept at 3.35 eV. The area of all fitting components for Pt 4f_{5/2} was constrained to 75% of the area of Pt 4f_{7/2} to keep the specific 3:4 area ratio for the two spin orbit peaks. The FWHM was below 2 eV and was generally allowed to vary freely during the fitting process. Constraints were applied only in rare cases to set a maximum allowed value to achieve a proper fit, particularly when multiple fitting components were used. The assignment of components during the deconvolution of the Pt 4f spectra was based on standard references [89] and literature reports [68, 90], accounting for the intrinsic BE shifts associated with the size effect of small supported clusters, as described in the main text of the paper. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity for better comparison.

5.7 | STEM

High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) images were acquired using a probe-corrected Jeol JEM-ARM200F NeoARM with a cold field emission gun at 200 kV acceleration voltage. All clusters were deposited onto holey carbon coated copper grids (Micro to Nano Company). Holey carbon (h.c.) was chosen for the high contrast with Pt, which allows for higher resolution images with respect to Pt deposited on metal oxide support. The cluster mobility on the carbon-based grids is considerably higher than on an amorphous oxide [91, 92]; therefore, the coverage of clusters was kept 0.1% ML to avoid agglomeration. Selected clusters were deposited on the h.c. copper grid with a predeposited 1.5-nm

layer of TiO₂ to study influence of the oxide support on the final structure of the clusters.

5.8 | Ex Situ XPS in Conjunction with ISS

XPS and ISS presented in Figure 7 were performed at The University of Utah using a Kratos Axis Ultra instrument, with a monochromatized Al K α X-ray source (1486.6 eV) and 300 \times 700 μm^2 analysis area. 10 eV pass energy was used, and the photons had an incidence angle of 54.7 $^\circ$ to the surface, and ejected electrons were measured orthogonal to the surface. Low energy He⁺ scattering was done using the instrument's sputter source operated with He gas and 1 kV beam energy, with He⁺ scattered at 135 $^\circ$ energy analyzed using the hemispherical energy analyzer. To minimize damage from He⁺ impact, scan times were kept as short as possible and the He⁺ beam was on only during scans.

Author Contributions

Initial planning and organization of this project were carried out by **Ingo Barke** and **Štefan Vajda**. **Magda Zlámálová** prepared the ALD supports, and **Hana Tarábková** measured AFM. **Mykhailo Vaidulych** synthesized the samples of the cluster-based catalysts. **Stanislav Valtera** performed catalyst testing. **Mykhailo Vaidulych**, **Stephan Bartling**, and **Stanislav Valtera** performed NAP-XPS characterization. **Kevin Oldenburg** and **Stanislav Valtera** performed HR-TEM measurements; and **Paulo Perez** and **Scott L. Anderson** performed ex situ XPS and ISS. **Federico Loi**, **Mykhailo Vaidulych**, and **Stanislav Valtera** analyzed and interpreted the XPS and ISS data. All coauthors participated in the discussion and interpretation of the results. **Stanislav Valtera** wrote the first draft of the manuscript. **Ladislav Kavan** contributed to sections related to thin oxide supports. **Federico Loi**, **Mykhailo Vaidulych**, **Stanislav Valtera**, and **Štefan Vajda** finalized the manuscript with inputs from all other authors.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Fig. S1:** Mass spectra of the molecular beam of pure Pt_n⁺ clusters with the Cluster Deposition Instrument optimized for the production of Pt₁₃ (top) and Pt₄₀ (bottom) clusters, recorded at lowered resolution to provide the highest flux of deposited clusters. **Supporting Fig. S2:** AFM height images (0.5 μm × 0.5 μm) measured in tapping mode for: (a) blank Si substrate with the native oxide layer; (b) 1.5 nm TiO₂ layer on SiO₂/Si substrate; and (c) 1.5 nm SnO₂ layer on SiO₂/Si substrate. The mean roughness R_a was 0.1, 0.1, and 0.2 nm for SiO₂, TiO₂, and SnO₂, respectively. **Supporting Fig. S3:** Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS Ti 2p spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/TiO₂ and (b) Pt₄₀/TiO₂. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity. **Supporting Fig. S4:** Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS Sn 3d spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/SnO₂ and (b) Pt₄₀/SnO₂. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. All NAP-XPS spectra were normalized to their maximum intensity. **Supporting Fig. S5:** Evolution of the high-resolution NAP-XPS C 1s spectra with temperature ramping from RT to 350 °C, acquired *in-situ* during the reaction of CO oxidation for (a) Pt₁₃/TiO₂ and (b) Pt₁₃/SnO₂. All spectra were normalized to the maximum intensity of C 1s peak obtained at RT to show how carbon content decreases with temperature. The first measurement at RT was conducted in an inert He atmosphere at the pressure of 2 mbar. Spectra were then recorded during the CO oxidation in a gas mixture of 2.5% CO and 2.5% O₂ at a 1:1 ratio (with partial pressures of 0.05 mbar for each reactant), both balanced in He, at a total pressure of 2 mbar. **Supporting Table S1:** XPS chemical composition obtained before (b) and after (c) sputtering for 3

different Pt₄₀/SnO₂ catalysts: 1 – after catalytic test at TPR, 2 – after NAP-XPS measurements, and 3 – pristine (as-deposited).

Biographies

Stanislav Valtera is a Ph.D. student at the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, Czech Academy of Sciences, in the Department of Nanocatalysis, supervised by Stefan Vajda. His research focuses on catalytic testing of subnanometer clusters with atomic precision and their detailed investigation. Stanislav aims to advance the understanding of catalytic mechanisms at the atomic level through experimental techniques.

Mykhailo Vaidulych is a researcher in the Department of Nanocatalysis at the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, Czech Academy of Sciences. He received his Ph.D. in physics in 2019 from the Department of Macromolecular Physics at Charles University. He then joined the newly established department led by Dr. Stefan Vajda, where he focused his research on nanocatalysis. His work focuses on the investigation of size-selected, cluster-based supported catalysts in various chemical transformations, using a range of *in situ* and *operando* techniques, with a particular emphasis on photoelectron spectroscopy and synchrotron-based methods.

Federico Loi is a postdoctoral researcher at the Department of Nanocatalysis headed by Stefan Vajda at the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Science in Prague. He defended his Ph.D. thesis in 2023 on the oxidation of noble and transition metal clusters supported on epitaxial graphene, supervised by Alessandro Baraldi at the Elettra synchrotron and University of Trieste, Italy. His current research focuses on the synthesis and characterization of mono and bimetallic size-selected clusters and their applications in heterogeneous catalysis, with particular focus on green chemistry applications.

Kevin Oldenburg is a postdoctoral researcher and the scientific coordinator of the Center for Interdisciplinary Electron Microscopy (ELMI-MV). He holds a background in experimental physics and completed his Ph.D. in 2020 on "Correlative imaging and spectroscopy on functional layers composed of nanoparticles and molecular aggregates." His research focuses on plasmonic nanoparticles and the coupling to their surrounding environment.

Ingo Barke is a senior researcher in the group "Physics of Surfaces and Interfaces" at the Institute of Physics, University of Rostock. His work addresses how nanoscale objects interact with surfaces and molecule crystals, using scanning probe microscopy and photoelectron spectroscopy. He actively pursues interdisciplinary collaborations that bridge physics, chemistry, biology, and medical sciences.

Magda Zlámlová was a staff researcher at the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, of the Czech Academy of Sciences and a Ph.D. student at the Faculty of Science, Charles University in Prague, under the supervision of L. Kavan. Her scientific interests focused on the electrochemistry of semi-conducting oxides and atomic layer deposition. Sadly, Magda passed away after a serious illness, just before completing her Ph.D. studies.

Hana Tarábková is a researcher in the Department of Electrochemical Materials at J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences. She has expertise in scanning probe microscopy techniques both *in ex situ* and *in electrochemical* applications.

Ladislav Kavan is senior scientist in the Department of Electrochemical Materials at the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, of the Czech Academy of Sciences, and professor of inorganic chemistry at the Charles University, Prague. Since 1988, he has

been a visiting professor of physical chemistry at the EPF-Lausanne, Switzerland. His scientific interests comprise spectro/photo/electrochemistry of nanocarbons and semiconducting oxides, including applications in Li- /Zn -batteries, dye-sensitized-, and perovskite solar cells.

Paulo Perez is a surface scientist in the Nanofab Lab of the University of Utah. His research focuses on nanotechnology and materials chemistry, using techniques such as transmission and scanning electron microscopies, and X-ray photon electron spectroscopy.

Scott L. Anderson is professor and the Henry Eyring Presidential Endowed Chair in chemistry at the University of Utah. His research focuses on nano and subnano scale surface chemistry, including catalysis and electrocatalysis with atomically size- and composition-selected metal clusters deposited on well

characterized supports, characterized by surface science methods, and studied using in situ methods. Cluster catalysis is also studied at high pressures and temperatures using a microreactor system. To study surface chemistry at ultra-high temperatures, a single nanoparticle reaction kinetics method has been developed that enables absolute kinetics measurements up to 3000 K.

Stephan Bartling is a researcher at the Leibniz Institute for Catalysis in Rostock and head of the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy team. He has a background in surface physics and chemistry and has conducted research at the University of Rostock and Chalmers University of Technology. His current

research focuses on the analysis of real and model catalysts using XPS under vacuum and near ambient- pressure conditions.

Štefan Vajda is a senior scientist and the funding head of the Department of Nanocatalysis of the J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry, of the Czech Academy of Sciences. He received his Ph.D. in chemistry from Charles University in Prague and Habilitation in Experimental Physics from Free

University Berlin Germany. Stefan initiated catalysis research on technologically relevant supports and deposited size-and composition-selected subnanometer clusters under realistic reaction conditions and their in situ / operando characterization using synchrotron-based grazing incidence X-ray scattering and absorption. The second main line of current studies includes catalysis by nanoscale materials synthesized by wet- and mechanochemistry